

Survey of Curriculum Quality of postgraduate studies of insurance management field Case: University of Allameh Taba Tabae

F. Havas Beigi, E. Mohammadi, M.Vafae Yeganeh

Abstract—Curriculum is one of the most important inputs in higher education system and for knowing the strong and weak spots of it we need evaluation. The main purpose of this study was to survey of the curriculum quality of Insurance Management field. Case: University of Allameh Taba Tabae (according to view point of students, alumni, employer and faculty members). Descriptive statistics (mean, tables, percentages, frequency distribution) and inferential statistics (CHI SQUARE) were used to analyze the data. Six criterions considered for the Quality of curriculum: objectives, content, teaching and learning methods, space and facilities, Time, assessment of learning. objectives, teaching and learning methods criterions was desirable level, content criteria was undesirable level, space and facilities, time and assessment of learning were rather desirable level. The quality of curriculum of insurance management field was relatively desirable level.

Keywords—quality, curriculum, insurance management, higher education

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING the last decades social demand for higher education has been growing, and that was a result of increasing enrollments despite inadequate financial capacity. During the years 1990-1991 to 2001-2002, the total number of students worldwide has increased from 68/6 million to 110/7 million people [1]. In Iran in 2007 about 2/5 million students were enrolled in higher education institutions, and more than 52 percent of those students were enrolled in private universities [2]. Development, diversity and privatization of higher education systems either in the developing countries or in the developed countries have been increasingly associated with the quality of higher education. Moreover, globalization has been strongly influenced by the higher education and new challenges for control and management has emerged [3]. Major global changes make higher education systems in all over the world able to meet local needs and global issues and consider the rapid changes in global politics and demonstrate traditional educational programs, quality and effectiveness more clearly [4].

F.Havas Beigi is postgraduate of educational management & planning from university of Tehran, Iran (phone: +98 0919 422 1529; e-mail: havasbeygi_f@yahoo.com).

E.Mohammadi is ph.d, faculty member of Ilam university, Department of management (+98 0841 2234850; e-mail: esfand50@yahoo.com).

M.Vafae Yeganeh is postgraduate of educational research from university of Tehran (phone: +98 021 22084084; e-mail: m.v.yeganeh@gmail.com)

II. COMPONENTS OF CURRICULUM

One of the most important and fundamental elements in pursuit of reaching the goals and national aspirations for the country's future generation education is the curriculums of the education system that should be identified according to the needs. On a final thought, the curriculum need-assessment consists of preparation of a set of essential strategies and decisions for curriculum adjustment and adjustment with the important needs that have priority [5].

A. Objectives

A curriculum is implemented to establish changes in learners' behavior. These changes are the same with goals of the program [6].

B. Content

A curriculum is more for teachers than it is for pupils. If it cannot change, move, perturb, and inform teachers, it will have no effect on those whom they teach. It must be first and foremost curriculum for teachers. If it has any effect on pupils, it will have it by virtue of having had an effect on teachers [7]. the effectiveness of instructional programme increases when teachers include reflection on instructional goals, students' characteristics and needs, content level and sequences, teaching strategies, materials, and other issues related to curriculum, instruction, and assessment before, during, and after lessons [8].

C. Teaching & Learning Methods

The prime responsibility of a teacher in an educational institutions teaching. Teaching is a complex activity. good teaching is a complex interaction of a wide range of teachers' characteristics, abilities, dispositions, knowledge of subject fields, experience, and pedagogical knowledge. These factors interact with particular school cultures, sets of educational goals, and children to produce effective teaching [9]. In any curriculum, special educational goals are considered that all learners need sufficient and different learning activities and opportunities in order to achieve them. So, it's not necessary to use a special method in any curriculum instead, different learning strategies can be used. Choosing an combined approach is recommended for two reasons: first, a special method may be appropriate for transformation of a definite amount of knowledge while inappropriate for transformation of other types of knowledge. Second, some of the learners

may learn better by using a special method while the others cannot learn anything using the same method [6].

D. Educational space and facilities

Curriculum doesn't just help students, but materials of any curriculum are provided by the potential learning opportunities for adults, namely, those who teach the material. Teachers still have a contradictory relationship with pre-determined curriculum materials like books. The teachers depend on the books to assist them and to use their instructions in the teaching process. Researchers have found that teaching materials specially books might not be high quality but they might be very limited; so, the teachers endorse learning and developing professionalism. Appropriate educational atmosphere and environment are considered to be one of the important elements of any curriculum since without an appropriate and desirable environment, prior stages of curriculum are affected and this seriously impedes curriculum implementation. For example, appropriate physical environment, the number of educational buildings and the laboratories, the library and workshops' environment, etc., can be mentioned that their number, extent, and physical quality can significantly affect the function of the educational system [10]. Most of the governments of developing countries allocate a large amount of sum to build educational institutions [11].

E. Time

Time is the fifth element of any curriculum, meaning that the content and the outlines of the defined materials are provided in a definite schedule. These time intervals are to be chosen in terms of duration and sequence in a way that can establish effectively perfect cognition and the required amount of learning in learners [12].

F. Evaluation

Effective assessment of scientific programs is to show the strong and weak points of different types of programs and provide a list of required information for assessment. Scientific assessment provides absolute recognition of curriculum for both university and faculty managers and introduces the field for the probable improvements. Assessment provides a list of resources for the students and introduces special fields to acquire skill and expertise in the universities. It also helps the new users of science and knowledge to know where to search for special skills [13].

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study is intended to evaluate the curriculum quality of insurance management field from different perspectives in the form of six basic questions:

- 1- How are the objectives in postgraduate studies of insurance management field?
- 2- How is the content in postgraduate studies of insurance management field?

How are the methods of teaching & learning in postgraduate studies of insurance management field?

4- How the statues of space and facilities implementation of curriculum in postgraduate studies of insurance management field?

5-To what extent the time been taken for curriculum implementation in postgraduate studies of insurance management field is optimal?

6-To what extent the method of assessment of students learning in postgraduate studies of insurance management field is desirable?

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is descriptive-survey study. Criteria and markers were used to conduct this study. Descriptive statistics (mean, tables, percentages, frequency distribution) were used to analyze the data. Inferential statistics (CHI SQUARE) was used to analyze the data. The method of weighting (valuating) was used to analyze the collected data and transforming the qualitative data into quantitative data. Respondents specify their level of agreements to the questionnaire using the Likert scale.

IV. FINDING AND RESULT

TABLE I
RESULT OF CHI SQUARE FOR OBJECTIVES CRETERIA

	Markers of objectives criteria	Result of statistical test			
		Rate of chi square	Rate of freedom	Level of significant	Level of desirability
1	Explicit and clear expression of educational goals	90/32	4	0/001	good
2	availability of goals of lesson outlines	47/53	4	0/001	Very poor
3	attending to upbringing the cognitive abilities in defining the goals	29/24	4	0/001	good
4	attending to theoretical skills in defining the objectives	9/39	4	0/03	good
5	attending to practical skills in defining the objectives	34/14	3	0/001	Very good
6	proportionality of goals with social and educational evaluation	16/31	3	0/001	good
7	the level of theoretical knowledge	81/53	4	0/001	good

For answering the first question we used 7 markers .the result of table I showing that the quality of curriculum's aims is in desirable level.

TABLE III
RESULT OF CHI SQUARE TEST FOR TEACHING & LEARNING METHODS

TABLE II RESULT OF CHI SQUARE TEST FOR CONTENT CRITERIA					TABLE III RESULT OF CHI SQUARE TEST FOR TEACHING & LEARNING METHODS						
Markers for content criteria		Result of statistical test			Markers for teaching & learning methods	Result of statistical test					
		Rate of chi square	Rate of freedom	Level of significant t		Level of desirability	Rate of chi square	Rate of freedom	Level of significant	Level of desirability	
1	The logical relationship between contents of the lessons	52/63	4	0/001	poor	1	Teaching the lessons by an expert teacher	30/32	4	0/001	good
2	providing the required fundamental and specialized concepts	51/67	4	0/001	good	2	using various teaching methods	41/67	4	0/001	Very good
3	complementarily of prior knowledge	38/11	3	0/001	Very good	3	encouraging the students to take part in teaching process	39/55	4	0/001	good
4	succession with undergraduate lessons	81/37	4	0/001	good	4	using group works while teaching	11/38	4	0/001	good
5	conformity with the last developments of the discipline	41/19	4	0/001	Very poor	5	using communication and information technology in teaching	24/83	4	0/001	good
6	upbringing the search-oriented spirit among students	95/32	4	0/001	good	6	conformity of teaching methods with the educational objectives	43/08	4	0/001	Barely acceptable
7	preparing them for specialized activities	32/151	4	0/001	good	7	conformity of teaching methods with the content	34/72	4	0/001	good
8	preparing them for doing independent research	44/27	4	0/001	poor	For answering question number 3 we used 7 markers for survey of desirability level of learning & teaching methods, the result of table III showing that the quality of learning & teaching methods is in desirable level					
9	upbringing the ability to investigate and develop research skills	37/81	4	0/001	good						
10	The connection between the content and practical needs of the learners	35/23	4	0/001	poor	TABLE IV RESULT OF CHI SQUARE TEST FOR EDUCATIONAL SPACE AND FACILITIES CRITERIA					
11	providing optional courses	51/76	4	0/001	Very poor	The markers for educational environment & equipment criteria		Result of statistical test			
12	The connection between volume of the content and the number of course units	39/484	4	0/001	good			Rate of chi square	Rate of freedom	Level of significant	Level of desirability
13	providing the content functionally and practically	31/62	4	0/001	Barely acceptable	1	The proportionality of the environment and the equipments with the number of students	24/46	4	0/001	Very poor
14	The conformity between the course units and the marketplace needs	63/09	4	0/001	Barely acceptable	2	availability of educational materials and educational support materials	27/54	4	0/001	good
15	applicability of theoretical courses	22/71	4	0/001	Barely acceptable	3	availability of research and study equipments	39/12	4	0/001	Very poor
16	applicability of practical lessons	39/13	4	0/001	Barely acceptable	4	availability of the appropriate informational resources	25/77	4	0/001	Very poor
17	proportionality of practical skills with professional services	23/47	4	0/001	poor	5	Proportionality of quantity and quality of educational environment.	33/19	4	0/001	Very good
18	The amount of Innovativeness and creativity	51/33	4	0/001	poor	We used 18 markers for answering question number 2 .the result of table II showing that the quality of content is in undesirable level.					

According to 5 markers in table IV we can get result that the quality of educational environment & equipment criteria is rather desirable level.

TABLE V
RESULT OF CHI SQUARE TEST FOR TIME CRITERIA

The markers for time criteria	Result of statistical test			
	Rate of chi square	Rate of freedom	Level of significant	Level of desirability
1 Timing the classes during the week	34/55	4	0/001	good
2 the time considered for the enrollment and examinations	57/73	4	0/001	good
3 conformity of the time and theoretical, specialized, and research courses	40/62	4	0/001	poor
4 the time allocated for acquiring the theoretical lessons	46/14	4	0/001	good
5 providing the prerequisite and compensatory courses in the most appropriate time	55/78	4	0/001	Barely acceptable

For answering question number 5 we considered 5 markers for survey time criteria. The result of table V showing that the quality of time been taken for implementation of curriculum is in desirable level.

V.CONCLUSION

In this research the important aim was the survey of curriculum quality of insurance management field and for reaching this goal we had 6 question .for answering these question we use 61 markers for evaluating different components of curriculum. According to result of research totally from 61 markers 17 of them were poor. These markers were: availability of goals of lesson outlines, The logical relationship between contents of the lessons, conformity with the last developments of the discipline, preparing them for doing independent research, the connection between the content and practical needs of the learners, providing optional courses, proportionality of practical skills with professional services, the amount of innovativeness and creativity, The proportionality of the environment and the equipments with the number of students, availability of research and study equipments, availability of the appropriate informational resources, conformity of the time and theoretical, specialized, and research courses, Assessment of manipulation and analysis capability, assessment of research skills of the students, creating new learning opportunities for the students, students satisfaction of the way they are assessed, conformity of the examinations and the content being taught. Other markers were in desirable level. in general the curriculum quality of insurance management field at university of Allame Taba Tabae were relatively desirable level.

TABLE VI
RESULT OF CHI SQUARE FOR ASSESMENT OF LEARNING CRITERIA

The exhibit for assessment of learning criteria	Result of statistical test			
	Rate of chi square	Rate of freedom	Level of significant	Level
1 Assessment of manipulation and analysis capability	75/90	4	0/001	poor
2 assessment of the learned knowledge of the students	39/75	4	0/001	good
3 assessment of research skills of the students	27/46	3	0/001	poor
4 creating new learning opportunities for the students	84/55	4	0/001	poor
5 students satisfaction of the way they are assessed	27/15	4	0/001	poor
6 conformity of the examinations and the content being taught	62/51	4	0/001	poor
7 conformity of testing methods and the predetermined objectives	60/71	4	0/001	good
8 conformity of testing methods and the content of the lessons	54/18	4	0/001	good
9 using various testing methods	62/07	4	0/001	good
10 attending to researches in the process of assessment	39/24	4	0/001	good
11 the amount of the skills and abilities in their professional field	44/92	4	0/001	good
12 creating behavioral capabilities	18/90	2	0/001	Barely acceptable
13 creating communication skills	18/56	4	0/001	good
14 creating emotional skills	11/42	4	0/003	good
15 observing the professional regulations	15/08	4	0/005	good
16 the amount of interest in work	34/20	3	0/001	Barely acceptable
17 the adjustment capability with the environment	12/95	2	0/001	Very good
18 sense of responsibility and job conscience	17/15	2	0/001	Very good
19 assessment of the learned practical aspects	16/55	2	0/001	Very good

Result of table VI showing that the quality of assessment of learning criteria is in rather desirable level.

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